

**NATURAL AND EXACT SCIENCES IN THE SYSTEM OF STEAM EDUCATION
TECHNOLOGY ON THE BASIS OF PROFESSION, STATUS AND MOTIVATION OF
PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES**

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Annotation. This article presents the pedagogical foundations of professional orientation in the system of natural Exact Sciences on the basis of STEAM educational technology.

Keywords: education technology, personality-oriented education, science integration, interdisciplinary interconnection, STEAM education technology, career orientation, technologist-discipline thinking.

In the first quarter of the 21st century, when the process of globalization of the countries of the world continues at a rapid pace, the process of integration of our country into the jaxon community puts a number of pressing issues before our national system of continuous education.

Higher education for the xxi century but as noted in the declaration to the world: "...the building the critical mass of qualified and widely educated people not to be able to stand adekvat higher education and research institutions could not have been real and ensuring sustainable development in any country..."[1].

"...The scientific and technological process that sets out for the civilization of the 21st century is a work and career gift for whoever is able to analyze, synthesize, evaluate his intellectual capabilities, as well as develop his adaptive mental and creative abilities well in relation to others-predictive fraud, written almost 30 years ago, very clearly defines the requirements for the training of modern specialists [2].

Such pressing issues the republic of uzbekistan "on education"of the law(the year 2020,September 23) and the "national training program"at ,as shown high potential intellectual abilities,the preparation of specialists having high moral qualities,that is, to have a deep theoretical and practical knowledge of the professors,the motherland and foreign life science products ,in practice use in the manufacture of can know that , armed with the idea of national independence,of high moral character, creative arts,business, respond to the requirements of the world standards of preparation of experts who can help the topical issues noted

[3.4].

To resolve this task using the rich spiritual world of the people of the achievements of science and innovation activities, widely base and universal, the concentration of the following times kadriyat national culture, economic and of science, engineering and technology education system based on the latest achievements of a perfect building, the society for the active-minded, imaginative and innovative ideas, supporting them in practice to prepare qualified specialists in today's society because it has the urgent need for rapid development during the period of active role-minded, imaginative and innovative ideas in practice required of qualified professionals that are effective in supporting them. This, in turn, innovasiyalar the education process, and requires the introduction of modern teaching interactive and creative methods [5].

Training of such independent thought, observation and logical thinking, creative, business, entrepreneurial specialists can be carried out on the basis of conducting career guidance, arming students with holistic, systematized theoretical knowledge, practical activity skills and qualifications using STEAM educational technology, which is used in the directions of natural Exact Sciences of the educational system of developed countries.

The above idea-thinking come out this article with students of secondary schools on the basis of modern education, which is one of texnolgiyalaridan steam technology, science, education, production of competition taking into account the essence of the science of physics science, technology, arts and mathematics integration engineering considering activity approach on the basis of professional orientation in the future of the profession to take that holistic, pedagogical knowledge provides the basis for the issuance of systematization.

The integration of the sciences, that is, fanlararo mutual connection didactic conditions, that is, when you put it on, not only on the educational process and systematization of reader-solid knowledge that increases student by mark proficient readers read of interests, theories, ensures that the scientific concept would be in a relationship with. As a result, it becomes apparent not only from the knowledge, and apply them in practice creates the opportunity to generalization [6,7,8].

Steam-powered technology on education analysis of the literature shows that this science technologists given to the integration of education technology-utilized engineering thought on the basis of theoretical knowledge, master the skills, qualifications and compensations with life, with practice, will go far towards the development of complex production method spiralsimon oddiydan the time provided by the students had surrounded us, and the universe are constantly in motion micro makro holistic, integral, integrity mean to intelligence it will help you to figure out.

STEAM technology education content consists of:

S-Science-Science. Development of knowledge, skills, competencies and competencies of students on the basis of scientific research skills.

T -Technology - technology. Development of students ' knowledge, skills, competencies and competencies regarding technology.

E -engineering-engineering. Development of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies related to the field of engineering of students.

A -art – art. Development of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies related to the field of engineering of students.

M -mathematics – mathematics. Develop students knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies in the field of mathematics.

STEAM technology education on the basis of practical methods of organization of training consists of the following.

Graders comprehensive high schools of education on the condition of steam technology, the level of development of their training activity, associated to the on the basis of group 5 will be :

- 1-group – Science - group of theorists
- 2 - group – Technology-group of technologists
- 3 - group – Engineering –engineer group
- 4 - group – Art - Russian art group
- 5 - group – Mathematics-matematiklar

Newton the theoretical issues of law to the students in the group, in their life, to be applied in practice and production, on the basis of mathematical formula and the graph is presented on the imaging task.

They are given a certain amount of time, then at the end of the given time, the decisions, feedback of each group on this topic are listened to and assigned to write them on a pre-prepared schedule, and a general conclusion is drawn by the teacher.

When you go to take lessons in the style of small groups, the following is achieved:

- active participation of each student and provides control and increases the possibility for the evaluation of their activities;
- provides a method to solve this problem quickly. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, and an investigation is underway;
- training of the student at any time of the interest group provides the opportunity to discuss

and inflated to the whole big;

- some students are hesitant to give their personal opinion on this topic to the teacher, while in small groups they exchange Free opinions with their groupmates, that is, actively participate in the training.

Small group sessions conducted to establish a plan.

1.The lesson plan is made to work in a small group, which is determined at the time of the beginning of the training.

2. Leaders are elected to their group. You don't have to do this, to give time to separate.

3.Problematic questions in a small group to work on issues or topics are selected. The purpose of the task to the students of the question and clearly explained.

3. Time to work on the problem is determined. Usually, 15-20 minutes is enough to make a decision on the issue in any topic.

4.Available to the group teaching training-visual materials can be given the possibility to use also.

5.Noise in classrooms to be teachers, some students become passive participants does not allow control of the activities of the group

that is the study of their mind.

6. Group leaders of public opinion on the subject in the form of the presentation of the group protects. Usually it is not recommended to give more time than 10 minutes for presentation.

7. At the end of the presentation, time is allocated for the debate, the teacher makes a general analysis of the problem, evaluates the activities of the groups.

The technology of teaching the subject of Newton's first law of the " dynamics " module on the basis of STEAM educational technology.

Basic Laws of dynamics I.Expressed in Newton's "mathematical foundations of natural Philosophy"(1687). These laws were discovered on the basis of experimental and theoretical research obtained before and by Newton himself.

Newton, based on experiments and observations, discovers his first law of determining whether objects are in relative peace without Candace and in what case are in a rectilinear planar motion.

Newton's first law is defined as follows: **if any body had the effect of solids him home until the condition of flat line or a bypass us peace keeps the movement.**

The effects of newton's first law a body of power to remain if it is moving with the speed

of change in terms of the size and direction of come to the conclusion that. The state of peace that is equal to zero, the speed of the movement while the private state.

The ability of bodies to maintain their calm state or rectilinear planar motion is called inertia. Inertia is one of the most general properties of matter. All objects, no matter where they are, will have inertia. Newton's first law is also referred to as the law of inertia.

The manifestation of inertia is faced by all of us with a vacuum. For example, while passengers maintain their initial position when the speed of the moving car changes from one, if the speed decreases — forward, if the speed increases — they deviate backwards. When a speeding horse suddenly stops, the rider continues his movement and falls over the horse's head. Due to inertia, the velocity of an object cannot be changed at once, which requires a certain period of time.

Table representing the first variant of the results of students working in groups based on STEAM educational technology under Newton's first law

<p>1-group S Science Supervisors</p>	<p>Inertia is an expression of the most general property of matter, expressing that it is in constant decay. If an object is not affected by force from the outside, it will move with a constant speed in terms of direction and Magnitude. When the body stops moving, it continues its previous state of motion. If an object is standing at rest its speed of movement will be zero. Of these, it is realized that Newton's first law can be defined as follows: If an object is not affected by other objects, or the equal constitutive of the forces acting on it is equal to zero, it maintains its calm state or linear planar motion.</p>
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<p>2-group T Technology Technologists</p>	<p>a) without saved changes suddenly when the wagon train moving on the speed of their initial situations, if the speed is reduced-forward, you increased the speed deviation will be back.</p> <p>b) when a fast-running horse suddenly stops, the rider sitting in the saddle goes over the horse's head, continuing his movement according to the law of inertia. If the horse suddenly runs fast from its position the rider will fall by moving backwards.</p> <p>v) a rapid sharp speed shift from the position of the bus, a stop from the collision, a deviation from one direction or another from the previous position of the passengers in it when turning left and right.</p>
<p>3-group E Engineering Engineers</p>	<p>In order to maintain the safety of passers-by, traveling by car, bus, train and plane, the modes of Transportation are provided with seat belts.</p>
<p>4-group A Art Fine art seminar</p>	
<p>5-group M Mathematics s</p>	<p>$v = 0 \text{ km/h}$ $V = 60 \text{ km/hour}$</p>

Based on the above considerations, this article provides pedagogical foundations for providing students of general education schools with a holistic approach-professional orientation - based, that is, holistic, systematized knowledge for their future occupation professions, taking into account the continuity of Science, Education, production, the content of physical science-

essence of Science, Technology, Science and mathematics

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